

Social food of Inthar ethnic group living in Inle Lake, Nyaung Shwe Township, Shan State (South)

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Abstract

In every society, food is a rich source of meaning, and people use it to communicate specific message. Particular foods and meals can draw people attention to each other, especially when they share and consume foods that symbolize concepts like home, family, or conviviality. Food preferences, etiquette, and taboos also mark social boundaries and identities. The three villages selected for this study site are Hea-Yar Ywar Ma, Kay Lar, and Inn Paw Khone in Inle Lake. *Inle* Lake is situated within Nyaung Shwe Township, Shan State (South). It is the second largest lake in Myanmar and unique for *Inthar* lifestyle. The aim of this study is to explore food related socio-cultural perspectives in *Inthar* ethnic group, who live in Shan State (South) in Myanmar. Specific objectives are (1) to describe the concept of food in *Inthar* and (2) to explore the relationship between food and inhabitant. Being field ethnographic method used, key informant interview (KII), and focus group discussion (FGD) were involved for data collection. A head or a top part of a *hinhtou* protruding out is a symbol of extending relationship between friends and relatives. On the contrary, trimming the extending banana leaves or no head sticking out of the pack symbolizes cutting the relationship with the dead and it also marks the last feeding for him/her. Such different ways of preparation indicate *Inthars'* symbolic meaning.

Key word; food, message, belief, practice, symbol, relationship

Introduction

Man has three basic needs, namely food, clothing and shelter. Of these things, food is the most essential need. Man can survive without other needs but it is not possible for him to survive without food. In society, food is needed not only for survival but in other sectors such as social, religious, and economic aspects of everyday life.

Social foods are foodstuffs consumed in the presence of other people and which have a symbolic as well as nutritional value for all those concerned. Whereas a meal or snack eaten in private is not a social food, all eatables of a family meal or all contents of a religious meal are social foods. In every human society food is a way of creating, and expressing, the relationships between people. These many examples of social foods illustrate the multiple roles that food plays in human society; creating and sustaining social relationships, signaling social status, occupation and gender roles, marking important life changes, anniversaries and festivals; and reasserting religious, ethnic or regional identities (Helman, 1991).

According to Brown (1999), the environment often determines what sorts of foods are available and also influences which foods are culturally preferred and which are prohibited. Culture is the final arbiter of what is acceptable to eat.

Inle Lake in Shan State (South) was chosen as a field locality. *Inle* Lake is situated in Nyaung Shwe Township. There are two reasons for selecting that of the study villages. As the first, the economy of the villages in *Inle* region is different from one village to another though they occupy the same habitat. The three villages selected for this study site are Hea-Yar Ywar Ma, Kay Lar, and Inn Paw Khone which are mainly engaged in goldsmith's and silversmith's works, floating garden respectively. The next one, almost all dwellers are *Inthar* ethnic group.

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Justification

Inle Lake in Shan State (South) is chosen as a field locality. *Inle* Lake is the second largest lake in Myanmar and has unique lifestyle.

Aim and objectives

This paper aims to explore food related socio-cultural perspectives in *Inthar* ethnic group, who live in Shan State (South) in Myanmar.

Specific objectives are

- (1) to describe the concept of food in *Inthar*
- (2) to explore the relationship between food and inhabitant

Literature Review

Dietary belief and traditional practice

Helman (1991) pointed out that food is more than just a source of nutrition. In all human societies, it plays many roles and is deeply embedded in the social, religious and economic aspects of every life. Food is an essential part of the way that any society organizes itself and of the way that it views the world as it inhabits.

Eckstein (1980) showed that food habit is a species term referring to the practices associated with consumption of food, e.g., the usual or customary items preferred and selected, the rituals of eating under variable circumstances, eating territory, eating times and frequency, meal climate.

Eckstein (1980) described that food ideology is a species term referring to the beliefs and attitudes of people that determine their personal definition of food and their activities in relation to food.

Food classification

Although the definition of food may vary depending on the standpoints of certain people, food is the most important basic needs for our survival. From the part of anthropologists, they have further pointed out how cultural groups differ markedly from one another in many of their beliefs and practices related to food. According to them, all of these stages in food consumption are closely patterned by culture, and are part of the accepted way of life of that community. What's more, foodstuffs people consume daily are found to be related to two factors: social relationship between individuals, and dietary belief and practices of a certain cultural group. Accordingly, the patterns of food consumption of a certain community cannot be changed easily.

According to Helman, there are five types of food classification systems despite several other systems may often coexist within the same cultural group. These five types of systems are: food versus non-food, sacred versus profane food, parallel food classification, food as medicine, medicine as food and social food system.

Helman study that the five systems of food classification described above illustrate how food may be eaten for cultural as well as nutritional reasons. From a clinical perspective, these cultural influences may affect nutrition in two ways: they may exclude much-needed nutrients from the diet (by defining them as non-food, profane, alien or lower-class food, or food on the wrong side of a hot/cold dichotomy and they may encourage the consumption of

certain foods or drinks (by defining them as food sacred, medicine, or as a sign of social, religious or ethnic identity) which are actually injurious to health. When both of these influences coexist there is likely to be an increased risk of malnutrition, manifesting either as undernutrition (a deficiency of vitamins, proteins, energy sources or elements) or as overnutrition (especially obesity and its consequences). Other cultural factors can also have an indirect effect on nutrition such as beliefs about the structure and functioning of the body, its optimal size and shape, and the role of diet in health and disease.

McElory (1979) studied that anthropologists are also concerned with the symbolic meaning of foods in different cultures and with the ways in which foods are combined to form culturally acceptable meals. French anthropologist Claude Levi-Strauss is especially well known for his analysis of South American Indian myths that elaborate on the themes of food and cooking. His book "The Raw and the Cooked" has more to do with symbolism and the structure of thought than with nutrition. Yet Levi-Strauss (1969-1964) indicated that "the gustatory code," the cultural message communicated by eating habits, occupies an essential and central place in human thought.

Nutritional anthropologist Jerome (1975) used interviews and participant observation to study cultural food patterns in black and white households in the Kansas City area. In a study of the decline in the use of the sweet potato in North Carolina, Fitzgerald (1976) found that sweet potatoes were seen as low-status "country food", despite their nutritional value, especially as a source of vitamin A.

Research Materials

Study design, study area, study population, study period and data collection methods regarding research methodology were presented as research materials.

Study Design

The research was conducted by cross-sectional and observational study.

Study site

Inle Lake, in Shan State South, was purposively selected as study area: Hea-Yar Ywar Ma village, Kay Lar village, and Inn Paw Khone village were included in it.

Study population

In this study, the study population was covered 30 persons in each village. So, a total of 90 person involved in it.

Study Period

This study was conducted during 2011 June to 2012 June.

Method

To collect data, qualitative research method including key informant interview (KII), focus group discussion (FGD), Direct observation (DO) was applied. KII was conducted with 5 persons in three villages. Six FGD were conducted in study villages to get information on taboos, beliefs and practices on food and concept on food.

Table 1. The population of three villages (2009-2010)

Village	Housing	Household	Male	Female	Total
Hare-Yar Ywar Ma	736	968	1596	1913	3509
Kay Lar	386	586	1303	1349	2652
Inn Paw Khone	261	341	594	786	1380
Total	1383	1895	3493	4048	7541

The concept on food

Food consumption is a basic activity as well as necessary bodily function to satisfy hunger for the survival of an individual. As rice plays a major role in *Inthars'* food-source, certain cuisines like medicinal bitter herb soup or *Seikharhin* is popular among them. In fact, it is their traditional dish highly valued by the folk. As its name suggests, this soup is made of a specific medicinal herb with a bitter taste. The powder used in the bitter medicine herb soup comes from bitter herb (chiretta plant) which is plucked in the cold season and then dried and pounded. This bitter herb thrives on mountainous regions of over 4000 feet. There are two types, the larger one and the smaller one. The one used in the *Inle* region is of the larger type. It is said that Taunggyi district produces the best bitter herb of the region. *Inthars* get powder and cook it with a mixture of various fruits, pulses, grains, fishes and so on.

Other popular dishes are Indian leak salad or *Allium tuberosam* root (*juu muiithau*), pickled fish salad (*Ngachin*), tomato curry (*khayanjnthee chet*), pounded soy-bean, mashed fish or pounded fish, braised fried fish or tenderized fried fish curry. The *Inthar's* favourite meat is fishes. The second most eaten meat is pork. For all occasions of joy or sorrow, pork is their favorite choice for entertaining people. Some villages prefer dried salt fish especially dog fish.

Regarding vegetables, *Inthars* usually eat mustard, carrot (*turnip*), chayote, cabbage, tomatoes. They use such edible oil as groundnut oil, sesame oil and palm oil. They tend to use more garlic than onion as the main ingredient in their recipe. They also use some spices in moderate amount.

However, man is social animal and no man can be an island. This characteristic is also manifested by the way people eat their meals. People tend to eat meals together with members of family or with members of a society depending on their purpose and needs. For example, a family meal with everyone in presence is not a mere eating time. It symbolizes not only enjoying a meal together but also a get-together party where family members can discuss matters, get help, advice and counseling from the part of the parents or has a friendly chat together. All in all, a family meal is a symbol of unity, warmth and security for all family members. In the case of *Inthar* community, it is found that family meals play a key role that their different and social food have different symbols and meaning in their life. The available food supply is prepared in their traditional way. They usually take three meals a day - breakfast at about 6 a.m., lunch at noon, and dinner at about 5 pm. Only a minority opts for tea, coffee and snacks in place of the boiled rice which is the staple food of the *Inthars*.

The relation between food and Inthar

In this session, two main issues are following

- (a) Social activities and food:
 - (1) Phaung-daw-U festival

- (2) Hare ya myitta paung ku festival
- (3) Initiation ceremony
- (4) Offering to Guardian Spirit and
- (b) Different messages of food
 - (1) The meaning of food in special occasions
 - (2) Prestige food
 - (3) A pair of foods that should not be consumed together are presented

Social activities

Phaung-daw-U pagoda festival

Thidingyut is the month for the famous Phaung-daw-U pagoda festival. It is celebrated from the 15th waning moon of Tawthalin to the 3rd waning moon of Thidingyut. The sacred images of Phaung-daw-U pagoda are made a processional journey along the villages of *Inle* region for the people to adore. Connections with social food are observed at Phaung-daw-U pagoda festival.

The villages which the sacred Images of Phaung-daw-U pass through 21 villages: veneration are Kyaye paw kone, Inn tain, He yar ywa ma, Nga phe chaung, Kyaye sa kone, Pwe sa kone, Lin kin, Nyaung shwe, Nan the, Maing thauk, Thale U, Kalar, Zayat gyi, Phaya pauk, Nan pan, Man kyee sait, Kyaing khon, Maing pyoo, Naing taw, In paw khon, Yai tha ywa for veneration.

Along the journey wherever the Images journey, the local people of that village have to entertain the people who accompanied the Sacred Images, the people who come to meet them and the pilgrims who come to pay reverence with food and drinks at meal times i.e. rice, bitter curry and fried dried fish and plain tea and traditional *Inthar* snacks.

Figure 1. Phaung daw U pagoda festival

Hare ya myitta paung ku festival

This festival is celebrated in Hare yar ywa ma village once a year known as Hare ya myitta paung ku (good will) festival. It is a traditional cultural festival to create friendship and good will among the *Inthars* living in the far flung villages of *Inle* region. The *Inthars* and *Inthas* can meet each other again in this festival. It is celebrated from the 10th moon to the 15th waning moon of Tazaungmoon. All the villages of *Inle* region load their white umbrella shaded

raft with all kinds of offerings and come to Hare yar ywa ma village. Then on 14th waning moon of Tazaungmoon, they are all offered at the Ywa U pagoda. They also send off fireworks display. Pilgrims from far and near can put up at any house and are fed with rice and curry meals as well as traditional snacks. The food served on these occasions include rice, pork, bitter herb (seikharhin), fried cattle hide flakes, fried dried fish, and 'juu' *allium tuberosum* root salad. Every house is full of visitors including strangers.

This "Hare yar myitta paung ku pwe" is called "san khon phwai pwe" by some *Inthars*. It means "May the bad news disappear and the good news arrive". In other words "it is a festival held once a year to meet and hear the good news, the auspicious message". A 70 year old woman explained,

"Hare yar event is one for relating good news group-wise".

Initiation ceremony

The *Inthars* being Buddhists, the boys of 10-12year of age are initiated into the Buddhist order. Some *Inthars* celebrate the Initiation ceremony during Nat tau and Pya tho (December-February). This custom is practiced as a communal family of relatives or a communal affair of the village.

They designate the days to call the would-be novices, the entertaining of the guests' day and the final day of attending the sermon. The children to be initiated are sent to the monastery to learn how to behave, conduct themselves as a novice, and learn to say the prayers in Pali and request the abbot to give them the robe and permission to enter the order. Then the boys have to go round to their parents and elders to pay obeisance. They are accompanied by two ladies who carry the pickled tea leaf tray and popped rice. They have to leave on the lowest rung of the elder's house stairs and near the kitchen stove a small amount of pickled tea and popped rice on a banana leaf. This is to pay obeisance to the guardian spirits or *nats* of the stairs and the stove.

Figure 2. Initiation ceremony

Figure 3. Offertory of miscellaneous things

The extraordinary thing is that all the preparations are made in the inner hall of the house if it is their own son but if the novice to be is an adopted son, the ritual is done in the outer room of the house. The guests who come to this ceremony are entertained with rice, pork curry, bitter curry, fried dry fish, fried cattle hide flakes and edible root salad. Sometimes, they give dried dog fish curry as a substitute for pork curry.

In this ritual of putting the cotton thread strands on the novice to be's hands, first of all they have to prepare an offertory of miscellaneous things. They are white and red rice pancakes, pickled fish, a male fish, a female fish (usually dog fish) edible root salad, flat cake, turned up cake, (9) kinds of fruit preserves, boiled big peas, popped rice and 2 combs of phigyan bananas placed left and right. Five to seven first marriage couples are chosen to prepare this offertory. They feed the novices to be with the food from the offertory, first a small mouthful as a token. Then the parents take the ring of cotton strands placed on the bananas and put one ring each on both hands. Each ring of cotton contains (9) strands. As they put them on the hands, they also pray for the blessings of long life and greatness in their lives. The guests also follow suit and put gifts in the big silver bowls placed in front of the novices to be. The children have a right to own all the gifts.

Figure 4. Thread strands on the novice to be's hands

Pregnant women are prohibited from attending this auspicious occasion as they are considered impure. If they should come, they must not put on the blessed thread ring. Also if a member of a household has gone on a journey, no member of that family goes to a *Shinpyu* (Initiation). The *Inthars* believe that ill luck would befall on that person. It is a taboo.

After the ceremony of putting gift thread bands on the hands of the novices to be the guests are entertained to a good meal. The “*Shin laungs*” novices to be dressed in their splendour are taken and shaded by gold umbrellas are taken in boats to the monastery where they are shaven and the abbot conducts the ritual of admitting them into the *Sangha*. The next day is the great day of the almsgiving and the sermon and the libation. This sort of alms giving is known as ‘*pwe*’ in the *Inle* region. The food served on these occasions include rice, pork, bitter herb (*seikharhin*), fried cattle hide flakes, fried dried fish, and ‘*juu*’ *allium tuberosum* root salad. Some with limited means do so without pork. Sometimes, they give dried dog fish curry as a substitute for pork curry. The men and women are fed separately.

Food provided for such occasion is measured by the *viss* (1.63 kg). The normal ratio of rice and curry is 100 *viss* of rice and 40 *viss* of curry. Curry in this context means the weight of pork curry served. In the measure for rice, the *Inthar*’s ‘*pyi*’ is made of 10 tin (condensed milk): of rice. Thirty ‘*pyi*’ of rice is needed to obtain 100 *viss* of boiled rice. For meals with dried fish curry, the proportion of rice and curry is 100 *viss* is to 6 *viss*. These are normal standards and there are variations in terms of differing villages. For instance, in some villages the rice and pork curry ratio is 100 *viss* to 45 *viss*.

A certain peculiarity is found in *Inthars*’ donation ceremony where on the number and names of invitees are not listed for invitation purposes, but only whole villages to be invited are listed. The population of each of such villages is taken into account for feasting purposes. Therefore an *Inthar* donation ceremony is found to be most generous.

(4) Offering to Guardian Spirit

Almost all ethnic groups have traditional belief concerning with foodstuffs. Another ritual of *Inthars* is Nat worship practice or paying respect to *Nats* or spirits. People from each village pay respect to their Guardian spirit of the village with offerings. The shaman or the master of the Nat worship ceremony presides to perform the rituals. To do so, each household has to contribute each quota of offering to this ceremony. The master collects their offerings and he makes arrangements to offer various foodstuffs such as white pan-cakes, red pan-cakes, and fried fish etc to the Nat. He respectfully offered them to the Nat on behalf of all people in this village and prays that all villages may be safe, healthy, peaceful and prosperous. He, then, divides the offerings into equal shares for all households. They all believe that they can be free from dangers and diseases and they will be peaceful and prosperous by eating these above mentioned snacks and foodstuffs being offered to the guardian spirit of the village.

Figure 5. Shrine of village guardian-spirit

Different message of food

(1) The meaning of food in special occasions

Such meal or foodstuffs served on various occasions including auspicious ones such as wedding receptions and novitiation ceremonies (known as 'pwe') and mournful ones like funerals express a relationship between individuals and between the members of a cultural group. However, the way people prepare the meals or foodstuffs varies according to the nature of occasions. *Inthars* have some specific practices to be adopted in these so-called social functions and occasions. It is the way they prepare the foodstuffs to be served that can identify the nature of an occasion.

Meals can also be used to symbolize economic. The economic status of a couple can be guessed by the style of their wedding reception. *Inthars'* typical social foods served on various occasions include rice, pork or dried fish, *seikhahin*, *allium tuberosum* roots salad; fried cattle hide flakes and a full complement of desserts. For wedding ceremonies the well-off serve these dishes while those who cannot afford the cost treat their guests to local off beat food called *Pauk choe* (popped glutinous rice snack (*Mayway*)), plain tea, betel quids, pickled tea and cheroots. Some entertain for seven days at a stretch with popped glutinous rice snack and plain tea.

According to traditional belief of *Inthars*, invitation cards for wedding ceremonies are usually distributed on the "Market Day" when several people from various villages can meet one another for their selling and shopping. They usually give out wedding reception invitation cards by the time those concerned have finished shopping or selling because they assume that these cards are not the symbol of good luck. On the other hand, invitation cards to a funeral can be given out during the sale time or shopping time as they are believed to bring good luck. Some people even tend to keep betel quid and cheroots given at a funeral as charms for good luck.

In other words, how they prepare social food gives us a clue to classify a certain occasion whether it is an auspicious one or not. Most *Inthars* usually invite the members of *Sangha* to preside their rituals and religious activities by offering them packs of fresh green tea leaves. Again they pack the tea leaves differently to indicate different purposes. A pack of green tea leaves for an auspicious occasion has a head protruding while that for a funeral has no head sticking out.

Some of the foodstuffs *Inthars* prepare and consume have symbolic value. For instance, the preparation of a dish of *juu* roots (*Allium tuberosum*) salad served at a wedding reception and that served at a funeral is quite different. *Juu* root salad, served on auspicious occasions such as novitiation and wedding ceremonies is prepared by separating the cluster of roots by hand in sticks in their original forms whereas that served at a funeral is prepared by cutting up the roots with a knife or scissors. The former type of preparation symbolizes growth, development or increase in their wealth while the latter marks the end of relationship with the dead person or cutting the attachment between the dead person and the bereaved family and or between him/her and every one present at the occasions. Perhaps friend and relatives alike a few people may prepare a dish of stir-fried vegetables to serve at a funeral. They use beans and cabbage to be stir-fried. Such a stir-fried vegetable dish is called '*seinn kyaw*' in Myanmar language. The Myanmar word "*seinn*" has two meanings; as a noun it means green colour and as a verb it means 'to estrange or to alienate'. *Inthars* seem to serve this dish to symbolize the estrangement to the dead or to cut out his association/relationship.

It is usual in the *Inle* region that burial follows the day on which a person dies. Meals for the *Sangha* (and the laity as well) are offered a week after as meritorious deed for the soul

of the departed. Food offered on such occasions goes in packs which contain kneaded rice powder, onion tops, salt and cooking oil wrapped in banana leaves (*Hinhtou*). The pack is steamed and served. A head or a top part of a *hinhtou* protruding out is a symbol of extending relationship between friends and relatives. On the contrary, trimming the extending banana leaves or no head sticking out of the pack symbolizes cutting the relationship with the dead and it also marks the last feeding for him/her. Such different ways of preparation indicates *Inthars'* symbolic meaning. With regard to *hinhtou* that is fed of funerals, one of *Inthars* also said as follows:

“When we treat the guests to hinhtou, we must not put out its head as it is the last time of feeding. However, for the other times, its head must be larger and longer too. There is a difference between auspicious ceremonies and inauspicious ones.”

Figure 6. Preparation for *hinhtou*

Moreover, some people serve the guests *hinhtou* together with fried crispies at funerals. With reference to this practice, there comes another ‘don’t’ for *Inthars* in their eating habit. An average house in *Inle* lake region is usually made up of two or three families. For example, there may be two or three families; i-e father and mother and unmarried offspring, that of the married offspring, that of uncle’s or aunt’s family either on father or mother’s side etc collectively living under the same roof. As almost all *Inthars* adopt extended family type, a household may consist of two or three families. Despite that, most *Inthar* do not cook meals collectively. Each of the families do the cooking on its own and dishes for daily diet of a family differ from that of another one. Because they think the dish *hinhtou* together with fried crispies is a symbol of a funeral, they always take special care to avoid the coincidence of *hinhtou* and crispies for the same meal in the same house.

(2) Prestige food

Some nationals regard some of the foodstuffs as prestige food/ostentatious foodstuffs because they are both rare and costly. As a result, only the rich and the distinguished guest can consume such ‘prestige’ foodstuffs. In *Inle* lake region the prices of common moorhen and natural small carp (*ngafein* *Cyprinus carpio*) have soared up. These foodstuffs used to be the hall mark of *Inle* region because they are *Inthars'* favourite foodstuffs. However, the majority of local people cannot afford to consume them owing to their very costly price. Nowadays they can be classified as ‘show off’ or prestige food.

Figure 7. Ngafein

A pair of foods that should not be consumed together

It was found that food taboos in the study area included belief on a pair of food which were said not to be consumed together. In some study (Zaw Aung, 1981) a similar belief was found for the health reason; if someone eats particular two types of food together he or she will become ill. But in this study area the reason for that belief is not only due to health reason but also for other spiritual and religious reasons. For example, regarding health reason some identified pairs of foods and the health consequences as follow:

Table 2 A pair of foods that should not be consumed together.

Sr	Name of a pair of foods if someone eats	Assuming negative health consequences
1.	Papaya and Turtle meat	Skin diseases
2.	Ginger and Pigeon meat	Skin disease (vitiligo)
3.	Jaggery (palm sugar) and pork	Diarrhea
4.	Mushroom and crab	Muscle tension
5.	Water melon and duck eggs	Vomiting
6.	Ice lolly and ginger salad	Vomiting
7.	Sticky brown rice and peanut snack	Vomiting
8.	Pickled salad and cow’s milk	Food poison
9.	Edible tuber and cow’s milk	Poisonous leading to death
11.	Mushroom and beef	Leading to death
12.	Mushroom and cow’s milk	Leading to death
13.	Pickled tea and water chestnut	Leading to death

Non health reasons to explain their food taboos as follows: *Hinhtoat* and fritters (*Kinpaung Kyaw* in *Inthars* dialect) because they are usually served only on the occasion of funeral ceremony. Another belief in food among study population is that sour snack is said to be harmful if it is consumed together with any pharmaceuticals because people think that there may be interaction between them.

Discussion and Conclusion

According to Helman, social food is also connected with symbolic food. Social food is always included in religious feasts. Besides it is also connected with the social, religious, or ethnic group as supernatural world. The Inthars as Buddhists celebrate all the religious festivals of the twelve months. Here is evidence of a religious feast with the social food flavor when the people taking part in a religious festival are entertained with food and drinks by the villagers hosting the Images of Phaung-daw-U pagoda in Thidingyut. The next day after the sermon, the guests are entertained with a full meal. The Hareya-Ywa-Ma Muiitta Paung Ku festival is a traditional cultural festival, where Inthars from far and near come to meet each other and exchange the good news. The guest who come are given a warm welcome whether he is old or new without discrimination. Pilgrims from far and near can put up at any house and are fed with rice and curry meals as well as traditional snacks. Every house is full of visitors including strangers.

A further example of a social food with ritual significance is the British wedding cake. Charsley (1987) suggests that the wedding cake- comprising three tiers, each one covered with smooth white icing and surrounded by elaborate ornaments and decorations is symbolic of the bride herself, in her long white dress and veil. Furthermore, the joint cutting of the 'virginal white' cake by the new bride and groom has a sexual significance-symbolic of the couple now 'becoming one flesh'.

Most of the foodstuff and consume on such occasions has symbolic value. It is found that *Inthars* follow traditional practices of preparing different dishes for different occasions. It is also seen in the symbolic pickled tea packet invitation to the Sangha. Moreover, even if the same dish or meal is served in both auspicious occasion and in funerals, the way they prepare the meal is quite different from one another. For example, some foodstuffs such as *juu muiythau* salad, *seim-kyaw*, *hinhtiut* etc served at such social gatherings bring about symbolic meaning. For wedding ceremonies, the well-off serve the visitors with rice, pork or dried fish and *seikharhin* whereas those who cannot afford the cost treat their guests to betel quid, green-tea, pickled tea and *paukchoe* etc.

Foods serve also as expression of prestige and social status in all cultures. Prestige demands that one should consume rare and costly items of food. Jelliffe (1967) studied among the prestige foods that can be identified are venison and game birds in Northern Europe, the T-bone steak in America, the camel hump among Bedouin Arabs, and the pig in New Guinea.

An interesting thing to be presented is the "prestige food" of *Inthars*. These days, with the soaring price of natural small carp (*ngafein*) and common moorhen, the majority of status symbol or prestige food because only the rich and distinguished guests can consume them. In this study Helman (1991)'s food classification has been applied in classifying *Inthars*' foods. Significantly in their traditional thinking, there are pairs of foods which should not be consumed together.

The Republic of the Union of Myanmar is constituted of more than 100 national groups. But their dietary patterns of food consumption vary from nationality to nationality, from place to place.

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